

Hydrolysis of the protein content of poultry slaughterhouse waste using alcalase enzyme in the fixed-bed system

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ORIGINAL RESEARCH ARTICLE

ABSTRACT

In recent decades, the demand of poultry industries has tremendously increased. Due to this, wastes generation from these industries increased significantly, which includes feather, head, bone, foot, blood, and viscera. These wastes can be considered as a source rich in protein and therefore utilized in various fields, including animal nutrition, health care, and compost production. To optimally utilize these waste resources in the feed poultry and aquaculture industry, the contents of the protein must be hydrolyzed. The enzymatic hydrolysis methods have been used for the production of high-protein hydrolysate. However, due to high cost of enzyme production, the use of immobilized enzymes getting lot of attention as they significantly reduce the cost of hydrolysis. In this study, alcalase was used for the hydrolysis of the isolated protein content of slaughterhouse waste. The optimal condition for protein extraction was determined to be 0.1 M NaOH, temperature of 70 °C and incubation time of 24 h. The degree of hydrolysis (DH%) of 16.6% was determined at a concentration of 5% (V/V). Alcalase enzyme was immobilized by entrapment method in the pumice stone. The hydrolysis process was carried out in a fixed-bed column. The parameters such as substrate flow rate and loading enzyme were investigated in the column. In the immobilized enzyme system, 128 mL of substrate at a flow rate of 0.1 mL/min was hydrolyzed and the DH% was determined as 4.1%. The function of enzyme in the immobilized enzyme system was determined to be $0.0044(U_{\text{enzyme}}/g_{\text{substrate}})$ compared with $0.135 U_{\text{enzyme}}/g_{\text{substrate}}$ for the free enzyme system. Also, the activity of the immobilized enzyme was maintained for up to 72 h in the fixed-bed column.

KEYWORDS

alcalase; entrapment; hydrolysis; immobilization; pumice

1. INTRODUCTION

World poultry production was more than 128 million tons in 2019 (Conway, 2019). Chicken and poultry products have 30% waste. Previously this waste was used in animal nutrition and organic fertilizers (Benjakul and Morrissey, 1997). The poultry slaughterhouse waste includes blood, feather, head, bone, foot, and viscera. Around 60% of blood, 90% of the feather, 50% of viscera, and 23% of bone are protein (Lasekan, 2013). These biomass solid wastes consist of proteins that are used as protein enrichment source (Cramer et al., 2007). Many efforts have been used, including enzymatic methods to produce protein

hydrolysates (Lasekan, 2013; Nchienzia et al., 2010; Fonseca et al., 2016). Protein hydrolysates are widely used in microbiology growth media and animal foods (Lasekan, et al., 2013). Enzymatic hydrolysis of the chicken wastes studied using diverse enzymes such as protamax, flavourzyme, alcalase, pepsin, and liquipanol. Alcalase is characterized as a more appropriate enzyme choice than other enzymes for the production of protein hydrolysates with high DH and recovery (Kurozawa, et al., 2008; Rossi, et al., 2009; Nchienzia, et al., 2010; Taheri, et al., 2011). Enzymatic methods are carried out under mild controlled conditions and maintaining nutritional values. Hence, it provides better and distinct chemical and nutritional properties for the

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hydrolyzed proteins (Maldonado, et al., 1998; Castro, et al., 2011). The subtilisins are protease enzymes that were obtained from bacteria such as *Bacillus subtilis*, *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens*, and *Bacillus licheniformis*. Subtilisins belong to serine proteases that initiate the nucleophilic attack on the amide bond through a serine residue at the active site. Subtilisins typically have molecular weights of 27 kDa. Subtilisin is also commercially known as the alcalase enzyme. Alcalase is a protease enzyme suitable for use in high temperature, moderate pH, and has good stability in aqueous solutions. The alcalase enzyme has an optimal pH of 7.0-8.5 and is active at a temperature of 30-65°C (Ottesen and Svendsen, 1970; Well, et al., 1983; Hadj-Ali, et al., 2007; Chen, et al., 1991). Generally, alkaline proteases such as alcalase demonstrate higher activities and DH than neutral and acid proteases (Diniz and Martin, 1996; Teshnizi, et al., 2020). The alcalase enzyme is commercially produced and used for a wide range of food processing applications, e.g. in fish and seafood processing (Fernandes, 2016), animal protein processing, and meat tenderization (Rossi, et al., 2009), plant protein processing (Anh, et al., 2020) and generation of bioactive peptides (Chen, et al., 1991).

The free enzyme systems are limited by enzyme sensitivity to temperature and pH conditions, difficulty in regeneration, high consumption of enzymes, and increased production cost. Considering the difficulties in using enzymes in free form, it is essential to develop the optimal technique for efficient usage. In recent years, the enzyme immobilization has been used in various methods with different goals and applications (Basso and Serban, 2019; Homaei, 2015). Enzyme immobilization protects the enzyme under various environmental conditions and enhances the enzyme stability and also enables reuse of the enzyme in continuous and batch modes (Dicosimo et al., 2013; Thompson et al., 2019). Various techniques and methods such as covalent, ionic coupling, trapping, and encapsulation have been used for enzyme immobilization (Brena et al., 2013). The enzyme immobilized has higher stability in different environmental conditions such as temperature, pH, solvent, and other in comparison with the free enzyme. Also, immobilization and reuse of enzymes reduce enzyme consumption and reduce process costs (Lindeque and Woodley, 2019). Due to the process advantage and economic benefits, immobilized systems are also attractive for commercial applications (Cao, 2005). To select the substrate as a matrix for enzyme immobilization, a range of properties should be considered such as,

available from a secure, convenient, and inexpensive source (Soleimani et al., 2011). One of the methods of enzyme immobilization is the trapping method. In this method, the enzyme is trapped inside the pores of the matrix (Datta et al., 2013). The enzyme molecule penetrates in the pores of beads and is entrapped but the substrate or product can be moved freely inside and outside the pores and the reaction can take place. The mesoporous silica (Ispas et al., 2009), sol-gel matrices (Erdemir and Yilmaz, 2012), κ -carrageenan (Tumturk et al., 2007, Jegannathan et al., 2010) have been used as immobilization beds in the entrapment method. The matrices selection criteria include high porosity, non-toxicity, biocompatible, amenable to chemical modification, and high affinity to protein (Betigeri and Neau, 2002). Inorganic supports have advantages over organic supports, such as low price, higher mechanical strength, high thermal stability, higher resistance to organic solvents and microbial attack, easy handling and, easy regenerability (Beshay, et al., 2011; Kourkoutas, et al., 2004; Gusek, et al., 1991; Weuster-Botz, 1993). Many inorganic supports were studied for immobilization such as palygorskite, montmorillonite, porous porcelain, hydromica, pumice stone, and glass beads. Pumice is a very lightweight, porous, and abrasive material and it has been used for centuries in the construction and beauty industry as well as in ancient medicines (Colagrande, et al., 1994). Pumice stone has been used in immobilization to produce a variety of biological materials by other researchers (Fiedurek, et al., 1992; Fiedurek, 2001; Beshay et al., 2011).

In this study, an enzymatic method was used to hydrolyze the protein content of poultry slaughterhouse waste. Alcalase has been used for the hydrolysis of protein content. Alcalase was immobilized by the entrapment method in the pumice stone beads. The protein hydrolysis process was evaluated in the free and fixed bed mode. The efficiency of the alcalase enzyme was compared in both free and fixed-bed systems.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The poultry slaughterhouse powder was supplied from the Etko organization in Iran. This poultry slaughterhouse generally includes the collection of industrial slaughter poultry waste, including head, foot, bone, viscera, and stuffed slaughterhouse. The slaughter poultry waste was cooked at 125 °C for 3 h. The dried brown powder was transferred to the

laboratory in plastic bags and stored until use at -20°C . Alcalase enzyme with the activity of 2.4 AU-A/g was purchased from Novozymes Denmark and was stored at a temperature of 4°C until use. Tyrosine and Casein were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Switzerland) and Folin-Ciocalteu reagent was purchased from Merck (Germany). The pumice stone was obtained from Kermanshah Company (Iran). All other used chemicals were of analytical grade and purchased from Merck and Sigma Aldrich Co.

2.1. Protein extract

Protein was extracted from poultry slaughterhouse powder by different concentrations of sodium hydroxide. The poultry slaughterhouse powder was added to 10 mL of sodium hydroxide in different concentrations (0.05, 0.08, 0.1, and 0.3 M). The mixture was incubated at 70°C for 24 h. The samples were centrifuged in 5000g for 25 min and then the supernatant was separated and the plate discarded. The amount of extracted protein was also determined using a Biuret Assay method.

2.2. Protein hydrolysis process by the free enzyme

The hydrolysis reaction was performed using alcalase enzyme of 5% and 10% (V/V) on pH 8 and at a temperature of 55°C . The pH of the reaction was checked continuously for every 10 min and the pH is adjusted to the initial value by adding 2 N NaOH. The amount of NaOH (2 N) used to maintain pH was recorded and used to calculate the degree of hydrolysis (DH%) by pH-stat method (Nielsen et al., 2001).

2.3. Enzyme immobilization in pumice stone

In this study, the pumice stone was milled and sieved using 0.5 to 1.0 mm mesh. The enzyme immobilization was carried out by the entrapment method. The sterilized pumice stone was mixed with 100 mL solution 10%, 20%, and 40% (V/V) alcalase enzyme. The mixture was incubated at 4°C for 3h. In the next step, pumice particles were separated from the solution and were washed 3 times with A buffer (NaCl 50 mM, pH 8) to remove the non-trapped enzymes. The enzyme activity in the pumice stone was measured.

2.4. Protein hydrolysis process by immobilized enzyme

The continuous hydrolysis process was performed by the immobilized enzyme in a glass-column, double jacket (14×1.4 cm, 15 mL volume). The buffer A was allowed to enter the glass column by a peristaltic pump, then the column was slowly filled with the pumice stones contains the immobilized enzyme. The glass column was stored at 4°C for 24 h the enzymatically hydrolyzed experiments were carried out at 55°C . The experiments were started by introducing the feed substrate (protein extracted solution) from the bottom of the column at the desired flow rate by a peristaltic pump. The effluent stream from the top of the column was collected in 5 mL aliquots. The schematic diagram of the fixed-bed system used for the hydrolysis studies is shown in Figure 1. The degree of protein hydrolysis was determined by the pH-stat method. The hydrolysis was evaluated at different flow rates of 0.1, 0.5, and 1 mL/min.

Figure 1. The schematic diagram of the fixed-bed set up for hydrolysis of protein

2.5. Measurement of alcalase enzyme activity

Alcalase enzyme activity was measured based on casein hydrolysis. In this study, a non-specific method for measuring the activity of proteases using casein as a substrate was used to determine alcalase activity. About 5 mL of 0.65% case in solution was added to four vials then they were placed in a water bath at 37°C for 5 min. The enzyme solution (0.5, 0.7, and 1 mL) was added and incubated for 10 minutes at 37°C . After this

10 min incubation, 5 mL of the TCA reagent was added to each vial and was incubated at 37°C for 30 min. About 5 mL of sodium carbonate and 1 mL of Folin's reagent were added to each vial. The vial was incubated at 37°C for 30 min and the absorbance was measured by a spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 660 nm (Cupp-Enyard, 2008).

2.6. Determination of the degree of hydrolysis

The degree of hydrolysis (DH%) was defined as the proportion of cleaved peptide bonds in a protein hydrolysate. Several methods exist for determining DH and the most commonly used methods are the pH-stat (Nielsen et al., 2001) and soluble nitrogen after trichloroacetic acid (SN-TCA), (Rutherford, 2010). The pH-stat method was relatively simple and was based on maintaining a constant pH during the reaction. Through pH-stat, the %DH was calculated from the volume and molarity of base or acid used to maintain a constant pH. The DH% was defined as the percent ratio of number of peptide bonds broken to the total number of bonds per unit weight (h_{tot} ; meq/g protein, calculated from the amino acid composition of the substrate):

$$DH = (B \times NB) / (MP \times \alpha \times h_{tot}) \quad (1)$$

Where B = base consumption in mL (or acid in case of acid proteases), NB = normality of the base (or acid), α = average degree of dissociation of the -NH groups or COOH groups, MP = mass of protein in grams (%N \times 6.25), h_{tot} = number of peptide bonds in the substrate (7.7 mEq/g protein).

This equation for %DH is valid when hydrolysis is conducted at a pH above the pK of the α -NH group (Kristinsson and Rasco, 2000).

2.7. Scanning electron microscopy test

The scanning electron microscopy (SEM) method was used to investigate pores of pumice stones and to determine the size of the pores. For this purpose, the milled pumice stone was washed and dried at 70 °C overnight. The pumice stones were layered with platinum particles and their surfaces were scanned by electron microscopy (LEO 1455 VP).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results indicated that extracted protein concentration was 7.4 mg/mL or 295.9 mg/g using 0.1 M NaOH. The effect of NaOH concentration on protein extraction is presented in Table 1. Increasing the NaOH concentration did not have a significant effect on the extracted protein. Due to the appropriate protein extraction by 0.1 M NaOH, it was selected for protein extraction for all the subsequent experiments. Figure 2 shows the results of protein hydrolysis using free enzyme 5% and 10% (V/V). The result indicates that during the start of the hydrolysis process, the highest amount of the hydrolysis occurred. Over 90% of the hydrolysis process was completed within 5h and the DH% was relatively stable until 24 h. The results showed DH% was increased when enzyme concentration increased to 10% (V/V) and the DH of 19% was obtained after 5 h.

Figure 2. The protein hydrolysis using alcalase in the free enzyme system

Table 1. The effect of NaOH concentration on the protein extraction

No.	NaOH (M)	Protein concentration (mg/mL)	Extracted protein ($\text{mg}_{\text{protein}} / \text{g}_{\text{substrate}}$)
1	0.3	7.47	298.8
2	0.1	7.44	295.9
3	0.08	6.65	265.8
4	0.05	5.60	224.1

Considering that the pore size of the bead is crucial for proper enzyme immobilization, it is essential to have sufficient information about the surface

morphology of the bead. The SEM results showed that the pumice stones examined in the present research had multiple holes and pores, as shown in Figure 3. The SEM images further indicated that the pores are 10-100 μm size, thereby confirming the possibility of entrapping the nanometer enzyme in the pumice stones. The pores with less than 1μm in the pumice stone are also visible. The high porosity of the pumice stone and having pores of different sizes have provided the possibility of proper immobilization of alcalase in the pumice beads.

Figure 3. The SEM images of pumice stone (a: Electron high tension (EHT)=19.00, Magnification (Mag)=50 X; b: EHT=19.00, Mag=200 X, c: EHT=19.00, Mag=1000X; d: EHT=19.00, Mag=2000 X).

Figure 4 shows the activity of the immobilized enzyme in the pumice beads. The results show that with increasing concentration of enzyme in the immobilization buffer, the amount of trapped enzyme in the pores of pumice beads, and the enzyme activity of pumice beads increased. The highest enzyme activity of pumice beads was 0.0069unit/g_{pumice} at 40% (V/V) of enzyme concentration, therefore, this enzyme concentration was used in the immobilization of alcalase in the pumice beads.

Figure 4. The activity of immobilized enzyme in the pumice beads

The effect of the substrate flow rate has been evaluated in DH% in the continuous hydrolysis process in the column. According to the result, DH% increased with decreasing substrate flow rate and as a result, increasing retention time in the column. Moreover, it can be concluded that more favorable hydrolysis occurs with increasing substrate contact time with the immobilized enzyme-containing pumice beads. Figure 5 shows the results of the DH% at flow rates of 1, 0.5, and 0.1 mL/min. The maximum degree of hydrolysis of 4.1 was obtained at a flow rate of 0.1 mL/min and a total of 128 mL of the substrate was hydrolyzed. The DH% was decreased to 2.9 on increasing the flow rate to 1 mL/min. The enzymatic hydrolysis was evaluated for the free and immobilized enzyme systems. The results are summarized in Table 2.

Figure 5. Comparison of DH in the immobilized system at three flow rates of 1, 0.5 and 0.1 mL/min

The maximum extraction of protein from poultry slaughterhouse waste using 0.1 M NaOH was obtained as 295.92 mg/g powder after 24 h incubation in 70 °C. The pH-stat analysis showed that for the

free system, the DH% was increased at the first 2 h of the hydrolysis process and after that, the DH% was reached the constant value by decreasing substrate concentration (Figure 2). The DH% was determined as 19.1% with alcalase enzyme (10% V/V) on the free system at 55 °C and pH 8.

Table 2. Comparison of enzymatic hydrolysis of extracted protein by the free (5%) and immobilized alcalase enzyme

No.	Factor	Unit	Free enzyme	Immobilized enzyme
1	Substrate volume	mL	100	128
2	Substrate concentration	g/L	100	100
3	Alcalase enzyme activity	U/g _{pumice}	-	0.0069
		U/mL	0.27	-
4	The Used Enzyme	U	1.35	0.0139
5	DH	%	16.6	4.1
6	The Used Enzyme per g _{substrate}	U/g _{substrate}	0.135	0.0044

The different concentration of alcalase enzyme was used for enzyme immobilization tests. The result shows the maximum enzyme activity of 0.0069 unit/g_{pumice} in 40% (V/V) enzyme concentration. The hydrolysis on the immobilized system is directly related to the retention time of the substrate in the column. The different flow rate of the substrate was investigated in the column. The maximum hydrolysis rate of the substrate was obtained as 4.1 at the flow rate of 0.1 mL/min, which was due to the long-time contact of the substrate and immobilized enzyme-pumice beads.

In this study, according to the results in the immobilized system, the immobilized enzyme could be used for at least three days. In the free enzyme system, the enzyme remains in the hydrolyzed media at the end of the process, consequently, the amount of enzyme consumption increases, whereas the enzyme can be reused in the enzyme-immobilized systems. Fonseca et al. (2016) investigated enzymatic hydrolysis of cobia meat and waste with Alcalase, Protamex, and Flavourzyme enzymes. They used ratio of enzyme to the substrate of about 0.1 U_{enzyme}/g_{substrate} (Fonseca et

al., 2016). Also, Nchienzia et al. (2010) investigated enzymatic hydrolysis of poultry meal with alcalase and Flavourzyme to improve the flavor of animal food products and they reported the ratio of alcalase enzyme to substrate as 0.01 U_{enzyme}/g_{substrate}. Nguyen et al. (2011) studied the long-term hydrolysis of tuna by-products (head, viscera, and tail) by Protamex protease and reported enzyme consumption was 0.01 U_{enzyme}/g_{substrate}. In this study, the results showed that the performance of the immobilized enzyme was been determined as 0.0044 U_{enzyme}/g_{substrate} compared with 0.135 U_{enzyme}/g_{substrate} for the free enzyme system.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The protein content of slaughterhouse waste was extracted and hydrolyzed by the alcalase enzyme. The results showed that in the free enzyme system, the isolated protein content was hydrolyzed with the DH% of 16.6% at an alcalase enzyme concentration of 5% (V/V). The function of alcalase in the free enzyme was determined 0.135 (U_{enzyme}/g_{substrate}). In the immobilized enzyme system, the DH% was determined 4.10% at a flow rate of 0.1 mL/min. The function of alcalase was determined 0.0044 (U_{enzyme}/g_{substrate}) in the immobilized enzyme system. According to the results, the performance of the immobilized enzyme system was at least 2.3 times higher than the results of the free enzyme system reported by the other researchers. Besides, the activity of the enzyme-immobilized enzyme was also maintained for up to 72 h in the fixed-bed column. One of the most important advantages of using entrapping techniques is the ease of the immobilization process and reloading enzyme on the column. This method has provided a relatively safe environment for the activity of the enzyme in addition to the easy, fast, and inexpensive method of enzyme immobilization. Due to the long life of immobilized systems, control of microbial contamination during use is crucial and can negatively affect the proper performance of the system and it should be considered.

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